

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND CULTURAL CAPITAL OF STUDENTS IN THE INDUSTRIAL TRAINING INSTITUTES (ITI) OF ASSAM

Limpi Talukdar Research Scholar Dept. of Education Manipur University
Dr. Chiinkhanniing Tombing Associate Professor Department of Education Imphal College
Imphal, Manipur

Abstract

The article aimed at to finding out the relationship between Socio demographic factors and Cultural capital of students in the Industrial Training Institutes of Assam. It is a case study conduct in five ITIs of Assam. The main objective drawn for the study it to evaluate the socio demographic factors and cultural capital of students in ITI of Asaam. Hypothesis of the study is that the cultural capital of students has nothing to do with the socio demographic factors of students. Main findings of the study is that there is no significant relationship cultural capital and age of respondent as evident by p value of 0.194. There is no significant relationship cultural capital and gender as marked by p-value of 0.518. There is no significant relationship between cultural capital and family size as manifested by p-value of 0.811. There is no significant relationship cultural capital and types of family as marked by p-value of 0.586. There is no significant relationship between cultural capital and over the three categories of birth order as evident by p-value of 0.459. The generalizability of the findings of the study would merit further investigation.

Keywords: *Cultural-capital, Socio demographic factors, Students, Industrial Training Institute, Trade.*

Introduction

In the present study, an attempt was made to work out and evaluate the socio-demographic factors and cultural capital of students in the Industrial Training Institutes (ITI) of Assam. In this context we shall highlight here about socio-demographic factors and cultural capital of students.

The theory of “*cultural capital*” was put forward by Bourdieu (1977, 1984). The concept “cultural capital” was coined by Pierre Bourdieu and Jean-Claude Passeron in “*Cultural Reproduction and Social Reproduction*” (1977). It was expanded on by Bourdieu in his essay “*The Forms of Capital*” (Bourdieu, 1985) and his book *The State Nobility: Elite Schools in the Field of Power* in 1996. Bourdieu described *cultural capital* as a person’s education (knowledge and intellectual skills) that provides advantage in achieving a higher social-status in society (Bourdieu, 1985; 1986). In the field of sociology, *cultural capital* comprises the *social assets* of a person (education, intellect, style of speech, style of dress, and all of the material and symbolic goods that society considers rare and worth seeking).

Technical education in India has grown under the pressure of necessity along various lines including industrial, engineering and technological training. This growth has been at two separate levels, once represented by colleges or universities and the other by schools. During the British rule, no comprehensive system of technical education was, however, developed as an integral part of the national system of education (Progress of Education in India, 1937-47, p.171, in Mukerji, 1960, p.260). The growth of technical education can be conveniently divided into three main periods, viz., (1) 1800-1857, (2) 1857-1902, and (3) 1902-1947 (Mukerji, 1960, see pp. 260-263).

Sullivan (2001) examined how cultural capital is distributed according to social class and educational level; the extent to which cultural capital is passed down from parents to children; whether male and female pupils possess different levels of cultural capital; and what effect cultural

capital has on GCSE attainment at age 16. The sample consisted of 465 pupils above 16 years of age in England, in 1998, selected from four schools, with two co-educational and two single-sex schools.

Sullivan (2001) studied the parental cultural capital on the basis of their occupation and educational levels in relation to the first research question – the distribution of cultural capital by social and parental education. The results indicated that “Service-class parents have a mean cultural capital score of 7.2, while non-service class parents have a mean score of 3.6”. on the other hand, “Graduate parents have a mean score of 8.5, while non-graduate parents have a mean score of 3.8 Both these differences are significant at the 0.001 level” (p.14). It suggested that parental higher occupational and educational levels are good predictors of higher cultural capital.

Regarding the second question: the extent to which cultural capital is passed down from parents to children, or to what extent is parental cultural capital associated with pupils’ cultural capital, controlling for background variables? – the results revealed that “Having a graduate parent and having a higher service-class parent are significantly positively associated with pupils’ cultural activities and it was significant at the 0.05 level. The Pearson correlation between parents’ cultural capital and pupils’ cultural activities was 0.617 ($p \leq 0.000$). The strength of this relationship provides support for Bourdieu’s view that cultural resources are strongly transmitted from parents to children” (pp.15-16).

With regard to the third question – whether male and female pupils possess different levels of cultural capital – the results showed that “Girls have slightly more cultural capital than boys in terms of both reading and other activities, and score more highly on the language test. Boys, however, slightly outperform girls on the test of cultural knowledge. Of these differences, only the difference in cultural activities other than reading is actually significant at the 0.05 level” (p.19).

Finally, the results on the question – whether cultural capital affects pupils’ educational attainment at GCSE (General Certificate of Secondary Education) examinations – indicated that “cultural capital is transmitted within the home and does have a significant effect on performance in the GCSE examination” (p.1). “the activities component of pupils’ cultural capital is a significant determinant of pupils’ GCSE score, as a parents’ cultural capital” (p.23). “Parents’ social class retains a large and significant direct effect on GCSE attainment, controlling for the cultural capital variables” (p.24).

To sum up, the findings suggested that parental cultural capital in terms of higher educational and occupational levels are significant predictors of higher cultural capital, that there are positive correlations between higher parental cultural capital and higher cultural capital of their children, that girls have more cultural capital of reading, other activities, and language than boys, while boys have more cultural knowledge than girls, and that students’ cultural capital and parents’ social class have direct effect on the academic achievement of students.

Rationale of the Study

The importance of the study of the Socio demographic factors and cultural capital of students had been highlighted above. Furthermore, such a study would be helpful in ascertaining the relationship between cultural capital and socio economic status as well as demographic factors of students. It will also help us in diagnose the how gender, Family Size, parental occupation, birth order related to cultural capital. The current study would enable the researcher to do further study about the cultural capital.

Objective

To evaluate the relationship between selected socio-demographic factors and cultural capital of students.

Hypothesis

Cultural Capital of Students has nothing to do with the socio demographic factors of students.

Methods

A survey was adopted in the in the investigation, in which five Govt. Industrial Training Institute of Assam was selected as a sample through the purposive sampling method. The sample was selected with a view to ascertaining the situations on the ground of the year of establishment and location.

Sample

The sample has been defined as ‘ a miniature picture of the entire group of aggregate from which population was selected’. In other words, it is the representative proportion of the population. For the present study the investigator has selected 300 sample from five it is of Assam on the basis of random sampling technique.

Tools used

For this problem entitled, ‘SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND CULTURAL CAPITAL OF STUDENTS IN THE INDUSTRIAL TRAINING INSTITUTES (ITI) OF ASSAM’ the major tool used was questionnaire. Students’ Cultural Capital Questionnaire (Noble & Davis, 2009) Questionnaire and Scale was employed in the collection of data.

Analysis of Data

To evaluate the relationship between selected socio-demographic factors and cultural capital of students

Table 1 (a): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and age of respondents

Age of respondent	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-value	d.f.	p-value	Remark
Adolescent	86	21.00	1.88	1.302	298	0.194	Insignificant
Young Adult	214	21.31	1.92				

** t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 1(a): This table displayed the relationship between cultural capital of student and the age of respondent of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of adolescent and young adult were 21.00 and 21.31 respectively. The mean variation was very minimal and statistically when applied t-test it was found to have no significant relationship cultural capital and age of respondents as evident by p-value of 0.194.

Table 1 (b): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and Gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-value	d. f.	p-value	Remark
Female	93	21.31	2.01	0.647	298	0.518	Insignificant
Male	207	21.17	1.86				

** t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 1 (b): This table demonstrated the relationship between cultural capital of student and gender of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of female and male students were 21.31 and 21.17 respectively. The mean variation was nominal and statistically when applied t-test it was found to have no significant relationship cultural capital and gender as marked by p-value of 0.518.

Table 1 (c): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and family size

Family size	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-value	d.f.	p-value	Remark
Small Family	163	21.20	1.90	0.239	298	0.811	Insignificant

Large Family	137	21.25	1.93				
--------------	-----	-------	------	--	--	--	--

** t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 1 (c): This table presented the relationship between cultural capital of student and family size of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of small and large family size were 21.20 and 21.25 respectively. The mean variation was very minimal and statistically when applied t-test it was found to have no significant relationship cultural capital and family size as manifested by p-value of 0.811.

Table 1 (d): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and Types of family

Types of family	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-value	d. f.	p-value	Remark
Joint Family	109	21.14	1.85	0.546	298	0.586	Insignificant
Nuclear Family	191	21.27	1.95				

** t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (d): This table showed the relationship between cultural capital of student and types of family of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of joint and nuclear family were 21.14 and 21.27 respectively. The mean variation was negligible and statistically when applied t-test it was found to have no significant relationship cultural capital and types of family as marked by p-value of 0.586.

Table 1 (e): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and Last examination passed

Last Examination Passed	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
Secondary	40	20.75	1.53	9.074	0.001**	Highly significant
Higher Secondary	228	21.13	1.80			
Graduation	32	22.50	2.56			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (e): This table exhibited the relationship between cultural capital of student and the three categories of last examination passed of the study samples. The highest mean score of cultural capital fall under the graduation category of last examination passed with a mean score of 22.50 followed by higher secondary category with a mean score of 21.13, and a least by secondary level of education category with a mean of 20.75. The variation among the mean scores revealed highly significant relationship between cultural capital and over the three categories of last examination passed as evident by p-value of 0.001. This finding indicated that cultural capital was found highest among student who completed graduation in their last examination.

Table 1 (f): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and grade in last examination passed

Grade in last examination passed	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
1st Division	52	21.19	2.13	0.346	0.707	Insignificant
2nd Division	154	21.15	1.82			
3rd Division	94	21.36	1.94			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (f): This table disclosed the relationship between cultural capital of student and grade in last examination passed of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of 1st, 2nd, and 3rd division of student were 21.19, 21.15 and 21.36 respectively. The mean variation was minimal and when statistically applied f-test it was found to have no significant relationship between cultural capital and over the three categories of grade in last examination passed as manifested by p-value of 0.707.

Table 1 (g): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and birth order

Birth order	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
1st Born	92	21.29	1.90	5.781	0.459	Insignificant
Middle Born	98	21.03	1.79			
Last Born	110	21.34	2.02			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (g): This table exposed the relationship between cultural capital of student and birth order of the study samples. The mean score of cultural capital of 1st born, middle born and last born were 21.29, 21.03 and 21.34 respectively. The mean variation was negligible and when statistically applied f-test it was found to have no significant relationship between cultural capital and over the three categories of birth order as evident by p-value of 0.459.

Table 1 (h): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and parental education

Parental education	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
Upper Primary	31	20.80	1.68	10.171	0.001**	Highly significant
Secondary	81	20.71	1.69			
Higher Secondary	147	21.21	1.69			
Graduation	41	22.58	2.53			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (h): This table displayed the relationship between cultural capital of student and parental education of the study samples. The highest mean score of cultural capital of parental education fall under the graduation category with a mean score of 22.59 followed by higher secondary level of education with a mean score of 21.21, next with upper primary level of education with a mean score of 20.80 and a least by secondary level of education with a mean of 20.71. The variation among the mean scores showed highly significant relationship between cultural capital and over the four categories of parental education as evident by p-value of 0.001. This finding specified that cultural capital was found highest among student whose parental education was under the graduation level.

Table 1 (i): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and parental occupation

Parental occupation	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
Business	107	21.12	1.85	6.607	0.001**	Highly significant
Farmer	43	20.65	1.74			
Government Job	82	21.96	2.21			
Private Job	68	20.86	1.42			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (i): This table demonstrated the relationship between cultural capital of student and parental occupation of the study samples. The highest mean score of cultural capital of student falls under the category of government job with a mean score of 21.96, followed by business with a mean score of 21.12, next with private employee with a mean score of 20.86 and a least by farmer with a mean of 20.65. The mean variation was found to be maximal and when applied f-test it was found to have highly significant relationship between cultural capital and over the four categories of parental occupation as marked by p-value of 0.001. This finding revealed that cultural capital was found highest among student whose parental occupation was government job.

Table 1 (j): Mean ± SD of cultural capital and monthly family income

Monthly family income	N	Mean	Std. D.	f-value	p-value	Remark
Below Rs. 25,000/-	46	20.63	1.73			

Rs. 25,000/- to Rs. 40,000/-	137	21.02	1.60	6.672	0.001**	Highly significant
Above Rs. 40,000/-	117	21.69	2.19			
Total	300	21.22	1.91			

** F-value is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* F-value is significant at 0.05 levels

Table 11 (j): This table presented the relationship between cultural capital of student and monthly family income of the study samples. The highest mean score of cultural capital of monthly family income falls under the category above Rs. 40,000/- with a mean score of 21.69, followed by an income level of Rs. 25,000/- to Rs. 40,000/- with a mean score of 21.02, and a least by an income level of Below Rs. 25,000/- with a mean of 20.63. The mean variation was found to be maximal and when applied f-test it was found to have highly significant relationship between cultural capital and over the three categories of monthly family income as manifested by p-value of 0.001. This finding revealed that cultural capital was found highest among student whose monthly family income was above Rs. 40,000/-

Conclusion

From the above study it can be concluded that in some variable the relationship of cultural capital is insignificant and in some variable the relationship is significant and highly significant. As a conclusion we can say that the relationship of Socio demographic factor and cultural capital of technical education is a very demanding and important Study area. The researcher covered only ITI but we need to cover all levels of education.

References

- Directorate of Employment and Craftsmen Training. Government of Assam. Skill, Employment & Entrepreneurship. Retrieved from <https://dect.Assam.gov.in/frontimpotentdata/list-of-industrial-training-institutes-o>. and <https://itiassam.nic.in/WebinfoCms/Page/Page?PageId=1&Langid=P>. Accessed 15th September 2021.
- DGT (Directorate General of Training, 2017). Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship. Government of India.
- Sullivan, Alice. (2001). Cultural capital and educational attainment. *Sociology*, 35(4), herein know as 2001, 1-27, 891-912. Retrieved from <https://www.socresonline>.
- Dumais, Susan A. (January, 2002). Cultural capital, gender, and school success: The role of Habitus. *Sociology of Education*, 75(1), 42-68. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3090253>. Accessed on 25 February, 2022.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1985). *The Forms of Capital*. In Handbook for Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education J.G.Richardson (ed.). Westport, CT: Greenwood. Retrieved <https://home.iitk.ac.in/amman/soo748/bourdieu-forms-of-capital.pdf&ved>. Accessed 11 February 2021.
- Chandler, Daniel.,& Rod Munday. (2011). Cultural production. In *A Dictionary of Media and Communication*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. *Oxford reference*